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**IMPACT OF EMPLOYMENT ON POVERTY REDUCTION
IN RWANDA**

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Degree in Applied Statistics

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Huye, July 2019

DECLARATION

I, Francois NSHIMYUMUKIZA, hereby declare that the work presented in this dissertation entitled “Impact of employment on poverty reduction in Rwanda “is my original work and has never been presented anywhere for any degree award.

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APPROVAL

This research project has been submitted for examination with my approval as a university supervisor.

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DEDICATION

To the Almighty lord,

To my elder sister

To my father

To my brothers and sister

Acknowledgment

I sincerely first and foremost, praises and thanks to God, the Almighty, for His showers of blessings through my research work to complete the research successfully.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

NISR: National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda

EICV5: Enquetes Integrales Sur Les Conditions de Vie de menages(Integrated Household Living Condition Survey)

ILO: International Labor Organization

R.D: Rural Development

SMEs: Small and Medium Enterprises

e.i: That is

CWR: Child Women Ratio

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ABSTRACT

This research assesses the impact of employment on poverty reduction in Rwanda. For this purpose, we tend to investigate the relationship between employment and poverty indicators. For the estimation of the ordered logit model, the stata14 software was used to analyze data from EICV5 and to establish the relationship and the level of significance between poverty status as dependent variables and the household characteristics, employment variables as explanatory variables.

They include the gender of the household head, education level, the main, major status, and sectors of employment. From the empirical results, households employed in Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers and the public have a higher chance of being poor. the factor that helps households' workers to avoid poverty are education level attainment (primary education, secondary and more education) followed by private farm and private non-farm.

The research suggests that modern technologies should be encouraged for households working in wage farm so as to increase productivity. Also, much emphasis should be put in education that should increase workers capabilities, competence, innovation and thus increase productivity although there is needs to design and to maintain and keep evaluationb to the strategies of poverty reduction to all area therefore will enable the household to overcome the poverty.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND

Unemployment is one in all the most important issues within the world particularly in developing countries and has so been a basic reason for poverty, however, has additionally been a result of the structural poverty in African economies each rural and urban. the shortage of sufficient productive Associate in decent employment opportunities could be a major bottleneck to reducing poverty and achieving the MDGs; it's additionally an increasing supply of social and political instability, (Olu, 2009)

(Olu, 2009)declared that whether or not they are subsistence farmers, salaried staff, or freelance entrepreneurs, poor individuals derive most of their financial gain from work. This basic reality implies that the extent of employment, the standard of jobs, and therefore the access that the poor must good earnings opportunities are crucial determinants of poorness reduction.

Similarly, (Pedro, 2013), a thoroughbred that Africa's recent economic performance has been quite spectacular. However, the robust economic process has not continuously delivered corresponding edges in terms of poorness reduction, part, as a result, didn't generate comfortable productive employment. His issues were, despite the robust growth record, African economies still face substantial economic and social challenges (Haroon, 2016)

For instance, AN increasing variety of teenagers aged between 18-24 years are getting into the labor market, so requiring economies to make additional and higher employment opportunities per country Youth Employment. Assessment report of (OECD, 2009) 67 % of the entire population of Rwanda is below twenty-five years recent. Lack of such changes has resulted in the high state among the youth. different social challenges embody gender discrimination particularly women in context to African norms that oppress the plight of girls to pursue their dreams in financial gain generation activities.

(Rizwanul, 2004)declared that the expertise of states, that succeeded in reducing poverty considerably, indicates the importance of sustained high growth in achieving this result. However, studies on poverty are replete with associate degree equally vital finding that top growth alone isn't adequate; the pattern and sources of growth moreover because the manner within which its advantages are distributed are very important from the purpose of reading of achieving the goal of poverty reduction. And in this regard, the importance of employment because the key link between growth and impoverishment alleviation is commonly identified.

Employment opportunities in most of African countries tend to concentrate in urban areas than in rural areas. However, the majority of rural dwellers are much vulnerable to poverty subjection that those in urban areas (WORLD, 2018) Contrary to this, According to EICV5 thematic report out of the 1.9 million (net), new people working between EICV4 and EICV5, the largest absolute increase in net new jobs have come from agriculture where 69.8%.are majority of workers in their main job worked in the agriculture sector. The largest percentage increases have come in mining (22% per year), construction (22% per year), and tourism (21% per year), all of which show an increase from a low base (NISR, 2018)

This implies that the largest source of employment in the agriculture of which it is widely practiced in rural areas and yet the majority of the rural population still languish in poverty. In rural areas, the challenge is great due to the many decent work deficits faced by rural workers. These include low pay, poor quality jobs that are unrecognized and unprotected by law, widespread underemployment, the absence of rights at work, inadequate social protection, and the lack of a representative voice (WORLD, 2018)

Although Rwanda is one amongst the poorest, most densely inhabited nations incontinent it's created spectacular progress in rehabilitating and helpful its economy once 1994 putting to death. the general economy has grown up at a big rate. the important gross domestic product growth averaged seven7% annually (WORLD, 2018). Exports have grown up by some fifty seven.6% annually since commodities; explicit gold, tin tantalum, tungsten, tea, coffee, generated over fifty-five of Rwanda, 86% of the population is engaged in agricultural production. Food crops account for about one-third of the country's gross domestic product, nonetheless food production typically doesn't keep up with the increase. Growth and profitableness during this sector are strained each by restricted access to land and also the terribly tiny size of plots that are on the market for

cultivation. additionally, thereto, the majority of Rwandans stay jobless, part-time and not well compensated (NISR, 2018)

In Rwanda, the general employment remains high at over 84% of the population aged sixteen years and higher than. the expansion in people in work has unbroken pace with speedy increment over the last ten years. the most important amendment within the employment rates over the last ten years has been for young people between the ages 16years and 24years. Their employment rate has born from 77% to 64% or, that reflects a positive trend of increase in educational attainment. Employment rates are typically higher in rural areas than urban areas and are the lowest of big capital of Rwanda known as Kigali city (NISR, 2018). This study thus seeks to determine the link between employment capability and poverty reduction in Rwanda country.

1.2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Unemployment issue is incredibly complicated however very crucial for peace, economic growth and poverty reduction condition. Any development which is not based on the creation of new works is not supportive of poverty reduction. Once people are out of work, they lack sources of income, they're insecure, and their living conditions rely on the society (the government, friends, parents...) unemployment affects also population increase within the sense that out of work people have lots of time on their disposal such sex might cause unplanned pregnancies. As a result, once the population is increasing higher than it will decrease the economy because the increasing number of dependency person, therefore, poverty can occur consequently.

One of the proper examples that most countries refer whereas gauging their performance in Singapore. This country took a whole turn-around step to develop the capability of their citizens through the development of their industry sector. This was the sole various that appeared viable by then, a state of affairs like Rwanda's restricted natural resources and little geographic capability vis-à-vis increment. The country gained independence in the early '60s once most of the African countries were liberating themselves from colonialism and then their economies were nearly at par. currently, Singapore is one in every of the developed countries whose per capita income is capable as one China and also the employment rate is high therefore the poverty level is low (NISR, 2018)

In Rwanda, off-farm and non-agricultural production have become extremely important elements of household survival strategies. Limited access to suitable land and low returns to smallholder agricultural necessitate a focus on urban-based markets. the largest-growing sectors in the industry were mining/quarrying and construction; the service sector experienced growth in transport, logistics, ICT and financial services (International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), 2016). Addressing the factors that affect household's participation in different types of employment and the income it generates from them will serve as a source of information for policymakers, administrators and other stakeholders for the benefit of the poor household in particular. Therefore, this study aims to assess the relationship between employment and poverty status in Rwanda.

1.3.RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Research this section presents the general and specific objectives of the study as below:

1.4.GENERAL OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of this analysis is to assess the impact of employment capability on poverty reduction in Rwanda

1.5. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- I. to investigate the link between household and poorness standing in Rwandese.
- II. to determine the consequences of employment variables on poorness standing in the Rwandese Republic.

1.6. Research question

The main analysis is targeted on the subsequent questions:

- i. What is the connection between household characteristics and poverty status in Rwanda?
- ii. however, will an employment variable have an effect on poverty status in Rwanda?

1.7. Research hypothesis

In order to adress the stated objectives ,the following hypothesis was tested

H1:there is significant relation ship between household relationship to poverty status

H2:there is significant relationship between employment variables and poverty status

1.8. The Scope of the study

The scope suggests each geographical and timeframe. the realm of study is covering the full country relevance the home survey (EICV5) conducted by the National Institute of Statistics in Rwanda (NISR) from2016/2017.

1.9. STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

The thesis is organized into five chapters: chapter one includes the introduction which covers research problem, research objectives, hypothesis, the significance of the study and structure of the thesis

Chapter two refresh on the literature reviews on both side employment and poverty. It also explains different theories on the employment and its relation to poverty reduction again some empirical experience on employment and poverty reduction relation are stated in this chapter.

Chapter three has to do with the methodology of the study; it plays up different methods and techniques used during the research. In this chapter we rely on the description of the study area, the source of data, the methods used to obtain data and theoretical and the econometrics model used to analyses the data set are demonstrated

Chapter four represented the analysis of the research and lastly, chapter five is about the conclusion and some final recommendations. After the summary of full research, the thesis put in place the further recommendation that can ameliorate employment opportunities as the key to reducing poverty

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0. INTRODUCTION

This chapter consists of two-part which is theoretical and empirical reviews. The theoretical review deals with employment and poverty in general, while empirical review deals with employment and poverty with evidence from other countries.

To understand the impact of employment on poverty reduction, it is better to understand the related concepts and some technical terms used in measuring employment and poverty such as:

Poverty definition

Poverty is the lack of ability to attain a minimum level of standard of living (WORDLD, 1999) This definition uses income and expenditure per capita to be enough when measuring the welfare and the two determine who fall below and above the minimum standards of living classifying them categorically from extremely poor, moderately poor and non-poor respectively.

According to (Gaag, 1990) poverty are an interlocking condition of few or no assets, underemployment, low wages and incomes, susceptibility to diseases, illiteracy, gender and economic vulnerability, social disadvantage, and political powerlessness. They relate poverty with lack of tangible property or inadequate materials.

(Chambers, 1983) defines a poor household as one with a small hut and few household facilities including furniture, mats or hides for sleeping, few kitchen utensils. The shelter is wooden, grass-thatched, or made with palms, fronds or hides. They have no latrines, have a small piece of land or none at all and a small or no livestock. The food and cash flows are low, unpredictable and insufficient.

Poverty is the deficiency, lack, and loss of social, economic, cultural, political and other entitlements, rights and benefits. These are rights that individuals, household and communities should enjoy in order to exist and survive in wellbeing with social dignity (UNDP, 2007)

Poverty is the lack of the means to satisfy basic material and social needs, as well as a feeling of powerlessness. Poverty is non-uniform, complex, multi-dimensional, cyclic and seasonal (MFPED, 1999). This definition indicates that poverty is beyond income and expenditures measurements. Poverty as complex as it is cannot be eradicated by a single standard solution.

(UNDP, 2007) provides a comprehensive definition of poverty; poverty is divided into two main categories: income and human poverty. Income poverty is divided into extreme poverty and overall poverty. Income poverty is defined as the lack of minimum income to provide for basic food needs (determined by considering minimum calorie requirements.) Overall poverty is the condition whereby the income is inadequate to satisfy essential non-food needs such as energy, housing, and clothes. Whereas, human poverty is the insufficient human capabilities, illiteracy, poor nutrition, which leads to a short lifespan, susceptibility to preventable diseases and inadequate material health.

The other side of the coin is necessary, that combines balanced, long-term and possible support that is specifically targeted to a certain location and dealing with seasonal pressures on households.

Generally, a poor household is one without basic needs, income, and productive assets. Different attempts to define poverty have created a situation that raised debate and came down to the conclusion that “poverty is subjective (Mansfield, 1986). (Kanbur, 1990) states that the poor in one dimension will become poor in other dimensions; they have limited access to public services such as sanitation and education compared with the non-poor. Consequently, this affects their income-earning capacity.

Poverty is multi-faceted. Simply, it is little or no household earning capacity (or consumption). The World Bank (1996) determined a poor person basing from a poverty line of \$1.25 per day in \$US 2005 purchasing-power-adjusted terms. In broader terms, poverty is the incapacity to meet primary necessities like; food, education, health care, housing, clothes, water, and sanitation.

Accordingly, poverty is a reflection of a combination of income household poverty at the level and poverty at the community level characterized by the poor provision of basic facilities, buildings, and services. An official definition of poverty must include insufficient income or consumption and limited or no access to land. Individually, a man or woman is considered poor if they are faced by inter-twined, complicated problems without financial remedies to cater for primary necessities like food, health care, childcare and clothes, and lose the capacity to provide for themselves. This can be analyzed from the local and national level; however, the required data is not available at the global level.

Poverty Lines

The starting point of every analysis is the poverty line, which bases on income and consumption data. The part of the population placed below the poverty line provides a quick indication of the range of the problem. A poverty line is a tool for measuring the acceptable economic level (WORLD, Annual report, 2010) Certainly, there is a clear level for what poverty is according to a given individual poverty line. In most communities, what consists “poverty” goes beyond the satisfaction of the absolute minimum survival needs. Poverty lines exist but are viewed differently in their location.

The poverty line is defined particularly by a given society according to its income distribution, and it measures that separates the poor from the non-poor, those whose income/ consumption fall below the line are classified as poor and those who are above as non-poor.

Basing on the current practice, the poverty line is estimated using purchasing power parity (PPP) exchange rates which compares the purchasing power of one dollar in different countries at different times. Hence the central concern of international Development Goal and Millennium Development Goal of reducing extreme poverty is the US\$1-a-day international poverty line.

The poverty line can be placed in relative or absolute terms. Relative poverty is the position of an individual or household in relation to the average country income, like a poverty line set at 40th percentile of the distribution. Relative poverty depends on the level of the average income.

Whereas absolute poverty is the position of an individual or household evaluated on a poverty line whose actual value is unchangeable over time. An absolute poverty line is based on the cost of the least consumption basket, that is set according to a recommended calorie intake. The poverty line is then added by the grant for non-food needs, that is solid with the consumption of the poor

In Rwanda poverty the official severely poverty line is measured based on the calories or consumption of the households, according to multidimension poverty report state that poverty is estimated after converting the household consumption level there fore poverty line based on the cost of foods on recommended nutritional requirements of 2500kcal per day (NISR, EICV5, 2018)

Employment definition

Employment is the set of all persons who reported in the labor force survey that they work as paid workers or self-employed for at least one hour during a specified period of time. The bureau of labor statistics classifies all person aged sixteen or older into 3 categories which are: the unemployed, the employed and the remaining category are considered to be out of the labor force. The most statistical indicator of employment is the employment-to-population ratio or employment rate in short.

Unemployment rate

The unemployment rate refers to the portion of the labor force that is unemployed. In other words, it is the percentage expression of unemployed persons to the labor force. An unemployed person doesn't have a job, is available for work and has actively looked for work during the past four weeks. Persons who have given up their search for work are not classified but are said to be "out of labor force". simultaneously, persons who scarcely intend to work at the present time may claim to be "actively looking for a job" in order to qualify for unemployment benefits.

Hidden Unemployment

Hidden or concealed unemployment has different concepts and manifestations. The concealed unemployment is the number of persons who are not included in the labor force due to their "discouragement over job prospects" and persons who are only "marginally attached" to the labor force. Discouraged workers are those workers available for employment, but presently not actively looking for work because they looked for jobs in the past but to no avail. Hidden unemployment should be added to the agglomerate of unemployed workers, therefore, the unemployment problem is importantly worse than it appears from the Bureau of the Labor statistics.

Underemployment

Basing from, the 16th International Conference of labor statistics adopted a quality definition of time-related underemployment. The new definition considers three factors. It involves all persons in employment who had a will to work additional hours; available for additional working hours, but worked less than a specified working time threshold.

Two types of underemployment: The open underemployed: persons who work less than full time and therefore cannot earn enough income to rise above the poverty line. The meaning of open unemployment and employment rates were taken as indicators of a well-functioning labor market has proven to be problematic in developing countries.

When there is no possibility of unemployment where a person can survive, some kind of work has to be found, often casual and informal work. Unemployment, therefore, should be understood according to the strength of the social safety net, the availability of informal employment and how much informal job is considered as underemployment due to formal employment possibilities. The disguised underemployment that is Nurkse-Lewis type surplus labor are persons who work as full-time employees, but at low intensity, within an institutional framework that allows both work and income sharing.

2.1.Theoretical review

(Lewis, 2006)stated that the economic growth is shown by the gradual movement of workers from the lower-paying segments to higher-paying segments. Moreover, they agreed that the central development problem is not unemployment but rather insufficient incomes in the poorer parts of the economy.

Additionally, they agreed that different incomes would be gotten by the same worker in different locations.

The human capital theory in the 1960s by (Schultz, 1991) and paid the two developers the Nobel Prize. According to this version of the human capital model, education and training improve workers' ability, helping them to work in different economic sectors and have more income. Other Nobel Prize winners have different views on the returns to education. Signaling models still affirm that workers acquire knowledge to show employers that their acquired education makes them more productive than other workers.

(Wachter, 1974)summed up the dual labor market model thus: Firstly, it is important to divide the economy into primary and secondary sector. Secondly, the employment and wage mechanism in the secondary sector is different from primary sector mechanisms.Thirdly, there is a sharp limitation of mobility between these two sectors, therefore workers in the secondary sector are

necessarily locked there. Lastly, the secondary sector is characterized by pervasive underemployment, due to that working person who can have training for skilled jobs at the normal cost are confined to unskilled jobs.

(Wachter, 1974) emphasized that the existence of labor market dualism depends on the condition that different wages must be paid in a different sector to the same workers. Evidence researchers then showed that comparable workers earned different amounts in different parts of the economic sector. On the other hand, skeptics such as Rosenzweig (1988) remained unsatisfied and maintained that the different incomes showed differences in unmeasured human capital. The unitary labor market model, in which all workers with certain skills receive the same wages despite which part of the labor market labor they are in; is a typical different model from the segmented labor market model. Consequently, there is poverty reduction when high economic growth is associated with high labor output.

2.2.Theories related to poverty

According to (Lewis, 2006)the poverty contributing factors to a community or an individual include vulnerability, inequality, economic alienation, and underdevelopment which often causes poverty.

Poverty and inequality

Inequality and poverty are different but also related conditions. Inequality involves wealth distribution in a population group, while poverty involves only those persons whose living standards lag below an appropriate threshold level (for example the poverty datum line). This threshold can be set either in absolute terms (based on an external factor, such as calorie requirements) or relative terms (for instance, a fraction of the overall average living standards.)

The relative poverty is tightly associated with inequality since the poverty definition clearly depicts the existing conditions of living of the whole population. Additionally, the majority of analysts argue that the movement in the Gini Co-efficient closely follows that in poverty. In contrast, this relationship is only established in countries whose comparative data is available. Therefore, it is not shocking to realize that the analysis of poverty often uses equality indicators.

This could be done in different ways, for example: through disaggregation: which connects measures of distribution with other poverty indicators; or by the description of a mathematical formula. Some analysts would argue that the reason for doing so, is that high inequality levels contribute to high levels of poverty in different ways, for example at any level of economic development or mean income, higher inequality refers to higher poverty, because only a smaller fraction of resources are available to persons at the bottom of the distribution of income or consumption.

Higher initial inequality can lead to lower successive growth and hence less poverty reduction. As an apotheosis, access to credit and other financial resources may be accumulated in the hands of a certain people, therefore the poor are barred from investments and this reduces the economic growth for the poor because an initially high inequality can lower the chances of the poor's advantage of growth. On the extreme, when all resources are in the handful of one man, despite the rate of economic growth, the remaining multitude will remain poor . (Sen, 1983)

Poverty and vulnerability

The international experience of poverty alleviation programs proposes that poverty is not a fixed condition among individuals, homes or communities. Instead, it is realized that, as opposed to some individuals or household that are permanently poor, others move in and out of poverty. This may be a consequence of life-cycle changes, particular circumstance like the illness of the principal breadwinner, or worsened external economic conditions. Because of the above quotation, the theory of vulnerability is increasingly applied to understand the change process. Actually, development practitioners tend to replace poverty with vulnerability, due to some combinations of vulnerability may be absolutely linked with poverty, i.e. female-lead households, families in isolate and remote mountainous places, minority group members, illiterate individuals, illegal immigrants, seasonal employees and so on. We should consider that however, the vulnerability is not equivalent to poverty.

According to the (WORLD, Annual report, 2010), vulnerability is the prevailing possibility or risk of being poor or being engulfed into deeper poverty in the morrow. This is called a downside risk. For example, vulnerability is a function of two main factors: exposure and response to downward

pressures. According to (shaffer, 2001), downward pressures are stresses (which are gradual and cumulative factors) and shocks(which are sudden and unpredictable).

Poverty and underdevelopment

The difference between poverty and underdevelopment is dependant on the definition given to each of the terms. Poverty is frequently regarded as a form of underdevelopment, when it is defined as deprivation of human economic rights, i.e. “ an economic condition where there are continuous low living standards in concurrence with absolute poverty, low economic growth rates, low levels of consumption, limited or no freedom to choose work that satisfies the human needs, high death rates, high birth rates, national economic dependence, inadequate health services and low income per capita.”

Otherwise stated, had human development been about expatriation of people’s choices (this was its definition in human development reports since 1990), then poverty would mean that chances and choices most basic to human development are denied. Contrary, the 1997 Human Development Report differentiates the two concepts by associating poverty with individuals and underdevelopment with a macro view. Therefore their difference mirror backs the two different possibilities of evaluating development.

One alternative center on the improvements made by all groups in each community, from the wealthy to the poor. This differs from an alternative perspective, the derivational viewpoint, in which development is evaluated by the means that the poor and the disadvantaged get along in each community. Provided the intimate relationships between these two ideas, it is affirmed poverty and underdevelopment have many characteristics in common.

2.2.1Types of poverty

Economic policy is instantly influenced by the definition given to the term poverty. Additionally, the magnitude of poverty is decided by the way in which the term is defined. The goal of this section is to distinguish different types of poverty.

Absolute versus relative poverty

Debates arose from the relative versus absolute poverty definitions. The definition of the two terms originates from the key concepts of difference and deprivation (Shanahan &Tuma, 1994). Therefore, absolute and relative standards, distinctively produce different deductions on policies

and accounts of the poverty experience and differ in terms of what the degree of poverty is ascertained (Townsend, 2003)

Absolute poverty is considered as an objective and scientific definition based on the opinion of existence. Specifically, it is a condition whereby an individual cannot provide for his longterm physical survival needs . This measure is universal and not time-limited, and advantageous due to its international comparability. A good model of this is the minimum amount of calorie intake recommended by recognized institutions like the FAO and World Health Organization, or the \$ 1 a day and \$ 2 a day that is utilized by the Human Development Reports when evaluating the magnitude of absolute poverty throughout the world.

In contrast, in an all-encompassing sense, absolute poverty includes several needs apart from pure physical survival, i.e. a condition whereby a person has not enough income to survive, based on the socially satisfactory conditions of life which include other essential commodities aside from nutritional requirements, for instance; clothes and a house in unfriendly climates. This broader definition involves to a certain extent relativity.

According to (Paul, 2013) a good model of this was given by Adam Smith who valued that the ownership of certain things such as leather shoes may be useful in one community to be socially acceptable, while in another society it is not important. Therefore, based on this view, the concept is considered to be downright, in that it developed from unsatisfied minimum necessities which are comparatively stable in a certain society. This is an explanation why some of the wealthy countries, like the United States (that use an absolute poverty line), have higher poverty lines than poor countries.

(Jalan, 2005)defined the short-lived component of poverty as one which is dependant on variability in levels of consumption, while the chronic component of poverty sums up what the poverty level would be if consumption did not change about its mean value. According to (Development, 2003) the most associated characteristics of chronic poverty include; human capital insufficiency, the poor demographic composition of households, lack or no ownership of physical assets and deficiency of low paid labor.

Chronic poverty is qualified by its long duration. Persons are chronically poor if they experienced privation over a long period of time. They may live in poverty during their whole lifetime and

frequently pass their poverty to future generations through their direct descendants. In addition to having an insufficient income, the chronic poor is often deprived in many other areas, especially education, health and dietary. Many factors keep them pinned down in chronic poverty, including living in distant rural places, little or no land proprietorship of land, livestock and lodging, inadequate education and skills, undependable and inadequately paying jobs; poor social connections, favoritism, and vulnerability to risks like diseases and drought (Micheal, 2010)

Factors that contribute to short-lived poverty are family size, government transfers, seasonal economic activities, migration and life cycle events. Crude evidence emphasizes that short-lived poverty is associated with fluctuations or shocks that adversely prevent families to maintain their consumption levels and this adversely affect their earnings or individual circumstances. (Jalan R.).

2.2.2. Causes of poverty

Factors that cause extreme poverty include:

Adverse geographic status that physically isolate the region (landlocked, island, mountainous area) and sparsely populated regions, unfavorable climate (hyper-arid, flood-prone), unreliable agriculture (poor soils, degraded land, inauspicious climate) or poor fisheries, insufficient energy resources (no fossil fuels, no hydropower), disease ecology (hyperendemic vector-borne diseases like malaria), major exposure to hazards like earthquakes, typhoons, droughts, and floods.

Good examples of areas with highly inauspicious geographical conditions include the Horn of Africa and the Sahel, which are landlocked, generally without fossil fuels, hyper-arid, drought-prone, endemic to tropical diseases like malaria and meningitis. A wide range of small island states are geographically isolated.

Prolonged violent conflict and international sanctions.

Violent conflicts and instability highly correlate with the incidence of extreme poverty. Afghanistan status has been diminished to wretchedness for the conflicts that prolonged to thirty years. In the same way, Haiti's economic status was devastated by concurrent episodes of international sanctions (WORDLD, 1999)

Despotic government and poor governance.

Embezzlement, corruption and the systemic poor distribution of national resources away from the needs of the poor, are crucial causal factors of extreme poverty. Despotic leadership in North Korea has led to extreme poverty despite all the economic favors. The inability of resource-rich countries in Africa to use their relative wealth to subdue the geographic disadvantage is another strong model of poor governance.

Gender and ethnic or social discrimination.

Indigenous peoples (about 400 million around the globe) and other debarred groups been extremely discriminated and socially excluded for centuries. Consequently, they incline their habitats in distant parts of the countries (c.f. adverse geography above) and constitute most of the poor shares in the extreme poor especially in Asia. The females continue to be extremely discriminated in social practices and legal rights(an example is the right to land title), worldwide this increases the risks of extreme poverty for ménages.

Employment-poverty reduction linkages

In order to study how employment greatly contributes to poverty reduction, it is important to distinguish poor people in the labor force from those who are not. Those who are not may have no one in the labor force to support them and would need some kind of social provisions so as to reduce their poverty. However, a bigger number of the needy people who are not in the labor force would actually be dependents of the first category of poor people, therefore their status will be without fail linked with each other. For analytical objectives, therefore, it is sufficient to concentrate only on among the poor individuals who belong to the labor force group. The poor people can be further subdivided into two groups: the unemployed poor and the working poor.

AS an empirical reality, it is true suggesting that the unemployed poor would constitute a countably less significant category in the poor nations. The logic simply is that the great majority of the countries have no insurance mechanisms, which are vitally important not to remain unemployed. As a result, the working poor would constitute by far the larger segment of the poor in the labor force. The sensitive issue with regard to the working poor is why they poor even though they are employed.

Two large categories of proximate causes would be divided into The underemployment and low returns to labor. i.e., the quantity and quality of employment determine whether employment would contribute to poverty reduction (Khandker, 2009).

Economic growth-employment linkages

Employment with increasing productivity is the main link in the growth-employment-poverty nexus. Increasing economic growth leads to poverty reduction if the productivity of poor workers increases, either in their current occupation, or in new jobs, or opportunities for self-employment.

In the ultimate study, economic growth will contribute greatly to higher employment and through higher employment, reduced poverty basing on three factors:

The growth factor: the rate at which the production potential of the economy expands, as represented by an upward shift of the production possibility frontier.

The elasticity factor: The degree to which an upward shift of the production possibility boundary boosts the employment Potential-Which is defined as the scope for improving the quality and quantity of employment. Meaning, our concern here is the elasticity of employment in relation to growth production potential.

The integrality factor: The degree to which the poor people are able to integrate into the economic process in order that, when growth takes place and the employment potential expands, they can have the advantage of the greater scope for improving the quality and quantity of employment. It may be important to make remarks on every described factor. Unless the economy's production potential is expanded, poverty reduction cannot be sustained, as determined by the growth of its labor force; sufficient human and physical capital, and technological progress. That expansion is the only one that can create the ground for a sustained increase in the incomes of everyone, including the poor people. (Khandker, 2009).

2.3. Empirical review on employment and poverty reduction

At the micro-level, various studies have proved the interplay between economic development, labor markets, and poverty under household surveys, wherein poverty levels are put together for a variety of household factors. A number of micro studies target employment as a major determinant of poverty. Ghaiha (1988) developed an analytical framework proving that poverty-reducing

effects are mainly from rural specific variables of development, new technologies, education and the gravity on the poor through various occupational group change basing on different variables.

(Islam, 2004) investigated if self-employment, casual wage employment and employment as “employee” have various implications for the probability of being poverty. (Islam, 2004) used logistics regressions with dependent variables as the probability of falling under the poverty line. Some variables for three factors of employment have been used as explanatory variables. Among them, agriculture was used as the base. An individual’s age, education, and household resources indicators were also used as households’ variables.

Under the regression factors, day workers stand high chances of being poor than the self-employed. The employee status is better than the wage worker because there is no significant positive impact on poverty. Similarly, other factors constant, the movement from agriculture to non-agriculture, increases the probability of rising out of poverty. Another similar survey was conducted on employment and poverty in Cambodia. This paper utilized a profit model to explore the intensity of the probable influence of employment on household poverty in Cambodia.

The way has been acquired from previous surveys by Jemio and choque (2003), comprising factors like employment, human capital and related assets; In addition, (Khandker, 2009)also utilized the profit, model in investigating the relationship between employment and poverty in Vietnam and Thailand respectively. In it were employment characteristics, income and ways of income production and the socio-economic environment as contributors to poverty.

Drawing from the description, from workers in the three major sectors, those working in services were the least likely to have poverty, while industries’ employees were nearly worse off the agricultural workers. Rare is any direct interpretation of the profit coefficients. Thus, minor results from the profit are weighed to interpret the effects the variability in regression apply on the outcome variable, indicating a high probability of being poor.

Under simple estimations, agricultural families stand higher chances of being poor than those households in the industrial sector. Under the survey, other crucial factors were found to determine the probability of poverty apart from employment factors.

Education of the head of the family, the number of family members between 18 and 64 years and the size of the household. Land decrease poverty in a family to a great degree. Paid employment, family size and members aged under 18 years are factors adding to household poverty.

In the same manner, Sundaram and Juresh Trndular (2002) investigating employment poverty to relationships in Madhya Pradesh (India) in a paper they used the profit model framework and studied the linkage in between the family criteria generally and their labor markets particularly and the chances of the family's poverty which is having monthly per capita consumer expenditure under the poverty line. Using regression outcomes, through family types separated by main ways of livelihood, Agricultural labor household contains the biggest part of families under the poverty line.

Factors of the socio-economic like scheduled castes and groups of the labor households are thought to be particularly not advantaged may be concluded to increase the chances of that family to be poor. Under the demographic factors, the survey's main concern was the child-woman ratio(WCR) or instead the attendant childcare needs in case women may be deemed to be to certain degree involved in the labor market activities and limiting them from mobility for skill formation through sustained on-job training or continuous formal learning. An increased (CWR) may be interpreted as a factor contributing to the increase in the probability of poverty in a family.

The increase in per capita land owned would reduce the chances of the family's poverty. The change from the status of owning milk cattle to having none increased the probability of the family being under the poverty line.

Under the absence of even a single regular wage for the paid employee through non-agricultural increases the probability of the family falling under the poverty line. Again, the study concluded that the effect of increasing the working days per week by the normal status employee in the family reduces the chances of being poor.

Other surveys use the categorical variable methodology in finding the factors to being poor. Geda et al (200) used family information from Kenya in analyzing the major determinants of poverty under both binomial and ordered logistics model. The outcome was that the education status, family size, and employment in the agriculture sector are highly related to poverty. In addition,

findings in the variables that were associated with poverty in the binomial model were also important in the ordered logistic model.

In Cameroon, Epo (2010) under binomial and ordered logistic regressions researched on determinants of medium- and long-term prevalence of poverty in Cameroon. Findings have shown that the age of the household head, education, number of working adults and infrastructure access are key elements related to few cases of poverty.

2.4.1. Employment and poverty reduction in Rwanda

Basing to EICV 4 and EICV 5(2018) surveys, household income is categorized into agricultural self-employment income, and non- farm self –employment, farm wage income, and transfer income. A specific concern is the pattern of poverty through economic activity proves that poverty prevalence is mostly found in families that get more than one half of their income from farm wage employment, meaning working on another person’s farm.

The next significant degree of poverty is found among people who are self-employed in the agriculture sector however a greater proportion of others in the category are not poor. It is quite vivid that for a big number, nonagricultural employment is the clear route to escape from being poor. This can be inevitable in areas where poverty is lower for those earning half or more of their income from this source, and from payments of self-employed. Poor families have greater revenues from farm wages than non-farm households.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1.INTRODUCTION

This chapter consists of the research design and methodology. The methodology is a set of methods and principles that are used when studying a particular kind of work or subject. (Lewis, 2006) This chapter concentrates on the source of data, the sample design, the variables of interest of the study, and the data analysis procedure used in order to fulfill the objectives of the study.

3.2.Research Design

Survey research design is appropriate where the study seeks to describe the characteristics of a certain group, estimate the proportion of people who have certain characteristics and make certain predictions (Churchill, 1991) to describe prediction without manipulation. A quantitative and descriptive research design was used in the study to investigate the views and the impact of employment variables on poverty reduction in Rwanda.

3.2.1.Quantitative

According to (Groov, 2001) quantitative research is “a formal, objective, systematic process in which numerical data are utilized to obtain information about the world “. Quantitative research design was used because this study focused on “number of specific concepts, used structured procedures and formal instruments to collect information, collect data under conditions of control and took special precautions to ensure objectivity”

3.2.2.Target population

Research population is defined as a generally large collection of individuals or objects that is the main focus of the study line and have similar characteristics. It is for the benefits of the population that research is done. A target population refers to the entire group of individuals or objects to which researchers are interested in generating the conclusion of the study, *Castillo*. The population study would be based on the secondary dataset from 2016/2017 EICV5 the survey provides data on the background of the respondent, economic, and main indicators which will be used in this research.

3.3. Source of data

This study was used a secondary data analysis that is obtained from 2016-2017 EICVS was the fifth Integrated Household Living Condition Survey conducted in Rwanda .the survey was conducted by NISR from October 2016 to October 2017.

3.4.Sample design

The researcher used the secondary data from the EICV5(Integrated Household Living Condition Survey in Rwanda) conducted by the national institute of statistics of Rwanda, a survey conducted in 2016-2017, the sampling frame for the EICV5 was based on the updated structure from villages. The urban and rural classification of the villages in EICV5 data was based on the corresponding geographic designation from 2012 Rwanda census of population and housing. The data set of the EICVS5 was used with the sample size of individuals is 64314 with 14580 households*NISR*. For the estimation of the logistic model, the stata14 software was used to establish the relationship between employment variables, household characteristics verse poverty status.

3.5.Variable of the study

The dependent variable is poverty status where the household is severely poor, moderately poor, non-poor. The main variables to be used in the study is household characteristics and employment variable. These will be broken down into smaller specific variables that can be easy to be measured and understood and they include the main occupation of household, main job status, job sector education level of household head, and demographic factor includes the gender of the household head.

The following table is all variable and their definition

Table 1: definition of variables

	Variable	Description	Definition
	Dependent variables		
	Severely poor, moderately poor, non-poor	Poverty	1=household being extreme poor 2=household being moderate poor 3=household being nonpoor
	Independent variables		
X1	Main job status	employed	0=Elementary occupations 3=Technical and associate professionals, managers 5=Services and sales workers 6=skilled_agriculture,forestry_and fishery workers
X2	Job sector	farm	0= NGO local, international organization and other specify 1=private non-farm 2=private farm 7=public
X3	Main occupation	employed	0=unpaid workers 1=Wage farm 2=wage non farmer 3=Independent non farmer
X4	Education level	Level of education of household	0=not educated 1=primary 2=secondary and more
X5	Gender	Gender of household	0=male 1=female

3.6.Data analysis

In this study, the analysis was done for poverty status where the poverty profile is topic to dig in. whether an individual or a household with a specific combination of characteristics end up with severely poor or not depend on the macro-economic situation and the kind of employment that household member are engaged in. this study aims to determine the determinant of poverty status, to find employment as the major determinant for poverty reduction in Rwanda we use logistic regression and descriptive analysis

The principal goals for this research are to discover the determinant of poverty status. to find employment as the major determinant for poverty reduction in Rwanda, we used the logistic regression. this method sought to explain whether a household is poor through categorical variables, by utilizing an ordered logit model. this is also known as the proportional odds model.

The dependent variables are ordered, where the variable could take a value of one (1) if the households are severely poor, two (2) if households are moderate poor and three (3) if household's is nonpoor

According to, with logit model one can interpret the dependent variables as the log odd ratio that a particular event to occur given values of explanatory variables. also, the estimation of the logit model uses maximum likelihoods (ML) techniques

Rwanda poverty status an ordered variable, and we have used the monthly per capita households expenditure to define whether the household is above or below the poverty line.

3.7. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics are important for summarizing the characteristics of the respondent for both categorical and numerical data, summary statistics were used to describe the collected data and provide general information about the selected variables, exploration analysis descriptive statistics including frequency table, calculation in percentages was performed and the research based on that to draw conclusion and recommendation

3.8. Multivariate logistic regression

According (Marija, 2001) Multiple regression analysis and descriptive analysis are two techniques that can help in explaining an ordered dependent variable from a set of independent variables. However, there is some problem in the interpretation of predicted variables as probability while their value is not in the range of 0 and 1, therefore, the answer to that problem is the use of logit function which helps in refining the relationship between the ordered dependent variables and a set of more than one independent variables

We use a logistic regression model which is suitable methods to find the probability of a household for being poor or being at danger of getting in poverty or the probability of household getting away to poverty.

The model was used for the purpose of examining the importance of households and labor characteristics for poverty reduction. This model analyzes the probability of being poor in relation to numerous independent variables which check whether someone is severely poor, moderately poor and non-poor

The model for predicted probability is given in the following equation

$$\text{Logit}(P) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + E_i$$

Through which: X1 is major occupation groups of house hold we expect that based on this variable poverty can be reduced at good extent

, X2 is jobs sector and also because people participating in job sector we expect that this variable will reduce poverty at higher extent

, X3 is main occupation status in each activity based on policy of government we expect the reduction of poverty

, X4 is education level we expect the poverty reduction according to level of education

X5 is gender we expect the reduction of poverty according to gender equality of our country Rwanda

where p is referred to the probability of household being (1 as severely poor, 2 as moderate poor, and 3 as non-poor), E_i is error term.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION, AND INTERPRETATION

4.1. Introduction

The study on the impact of employment on poverty reduction in Rwanda, therefore, this chapter contain the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of data obtain from EICV5 2016/2017. This chapter is organized into different session one is descriptive analysis where it will present frequency, the cross-tabulation second is multivariate analysis using ordered logistic model is used to present relationship between poverty status as the dependent variable and employment variable, household characteristics as independent variables.

4.2. Background feature of Respondents

This mentions the descriptive summary of the background's characteristics of 14,580 household respondents sampled in 2016/2017 EICV5. The information that households provide is important for understanding the impact of employment on poverty reduction based on the household's characteristics and their living condition also concerning the education level and other factors these characteristics were chosen based on the report of EICVS5

4.3. Descriptive statistics Analysis

The descriptive statistics are very crucial to sum-up the characteristics of the respondents for both categorical and numerical data ,summary statistics was done to describe the collected data and giving the general information about selected variables, exploration analysis descriptive statistics including frequency table, and also displayed using graphs to analyze the data collected basing on the number of respondents ,calculation in percentages was performed and the researcher based on that to draw conclusion and recommendations.

Study variable	Poverty status			N
	Severely poor(%)	Moderate poor(%)	Non poor(%)	
Total				14,580
Main occupation				
Services and sales workers	251(11.01)	440(19.30)	1,589(69.69)	2,280
Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers	796(14.37)	1,121(20.24)	1,589(65.39)	5,539
elementary occupation	693(13.08)	1,102(20.80)	3,503(66.12)	5,298
Technical and associate professionals, managers	166(11.35)	268(18.32)	1,029(70.33)	1,463
Job sector				
NGO_local,international organization and other specify	187(12.80)	251(17.18)	1,023(70.02)	1,461
private non-farm	560(11.91)	917(19.51)	3,223(68.57)	4,700
private farm	1,051(14.02)	1,564(20.86)	4,882(65.12)	7,497
Public	108(11.71)	199(21.58)	615(66.70)	922
Main Job Status				
Wage farm	353(13.73)	536(20.85)	1,682(65.42)	2,571
Wage non-farm	438(11.87)	719(19.48)	2,534(68.65)	3,691
Independent farmer	542(14.08)	789(20.49)	2,519(65.43)	3,850
unpaid workers	573(12.82)	887(19.85)	3,008(67.32)	4,468
Education level				
not educated	939(14.50)	1,397(21.58)	4,139(63.92)	6,475
Primary	635(12.20)	970(18.63)	3,602(69.18)	5,207
secondary and more	332(11.46)	564(19.46)	2,002(69.08)	69.08
Gender				
Male	916(13.00)	1,418(20.13)	4,710(66.87)	7,044
Female	990(13.14)	1,513(20.08)	5,033(66.79)	7,536

Table 2: descriptive table

According to table 2 poverty status is tend to 13.07% as severely poor and 20.10% for moderate poor and also 66.8% or 14800 household and it seen that both severely and moderate are poor therefore we can state that poorness to this household are about 33.80% which is serious problem to these household head therefore the living condition of child and relative is very worse, therefore we present this statistics to know area with higher number of poverty status among employment variables and household characteristics.

According to **Main occupation** those in service and sales workers are less likely to be poor based on number of household in severely poor which is equal to 11.01% of the household means that people in service they tend to be free from poverty and it can be caused with many factors to be discussed later

According to education level people not educated have large number in severely poor categories therefore being non educated increase the chance of being severely poor while people educated have large number of those who are non poor it because most of job are based on skills

As conclusion based on this **table 2** people in service and sales work have large number of people who are non poor, it is meaningful that people who are educated are those who are in service and sales works.

Lastly poverty according to gender it seen that female have large number who are poor but these means that by government support to female is useful but some female became lazy to the work and does not find work for improvement therefore cause them to stay in one categories .

4.4. Multivariate analysis

Multivariate analysis was used to examine the relationship between each independent variables and poverty status by using ordered logistic regression where logit model the slope coefficient of a variable gives the change in the log of odds associated with the unit change in that variable, and by evaluating the marginal effect which measure the direct the change in probability of an event

occurring as the result of a unit change in the value s of a regressor, with the effect of all other variables held constant.

The ordered logistic regression model

Table 3: ordered logistic table

Table 3

Variables in the equation(reg)	β	Odds ratio	S.E.	Sig.	Marginal effect		
					dy/dx(severely poor)	dy/dx(moderate poor)	dy/dx(non poor)
Employment variables							
Elementary occupations(Ref.cat.)							
Technical and associate professionals, managers	0.2132092	1.237644	0.072	0.003	-0.022***	-0.022***	0.045***
Services and sales workers	0.1635747	1.177713	0.073	0.027	-0.017***	-0.0176354***	0.035***
Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers	-0.0627021	0.9392232	0.112	0.578	0.007	0.006	-0.014
NGO local, international organization and other specify (Ref.cat.)							
Private_non-farm	-0.494	0.609	0.090	0.000	-0.053***	-0.052***	0.010***
private farm	-0.265	0.767	0.079	0.001	-0.026***	-0.0280389***	0.054***
Public	-0.380	0.683	0.118	0.001	0.039***	.040***	-0.079***
unpaid workers(Ref.cat.)							
wage farm	0.0565137	0.9450536	0.112	0.616	0.006	0.006	-0.012
Wage_non-farm	-0.015186	1.015302	0.069	0.827	-0.001	-0.001	0.003
Independent farmer	-0.014965	0.9851465	0.053	0.780	0.001	0.001	-0.003
Household characteristics (Ref.cat.)							
Male	Reference						
Female	-0.009	0.99	0.034	0.783	0.001	0.001	-0.002
not educated	Reference						
Primary	0.335	1.398	0.0510893	0.000	-0.038***	-0.035***	0.074***

secondary and more	0.325	1.385	0.055	0.000	-0.037***	-0.0348821***	0.0723***

Number of observations =14580
 LR Chi2(12) =87.84
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 Log likelihood = -12463.753
 Pseudo R2 =0.0035
 Note that Note: dy/dx for factor levels is the discrete change from the base level

***P-Value<0.05 model used data from the NISR, EICV5(2016-2017)

4.5. Interpretation of the result

The use of the ordered logit model enabled the study to look at how a particular variable affects the magnitude of household poverty status. The results are subdivided into two parts such as employment variables and household characteristics as stated in the section below:

4.5.1. Employment variables

In this part, we analyze the determinants of poverty from employment variables where employment differ in many aspects including major occupation groups, sector of job and occupational status in each activity. This will help us for specifically to understand why some household are able to reduce poverty status than others when there are working in different occupational groups (Elementary occupations, Technical and associate professionals’ managers, Services and sales workers, Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers) and others

From the analysis, the result indicates that some of the variables which account for an increase in poverty status include Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers.

The result from the study indicates that one-unit change increase chance of household in occupation groups of Technical and associate professionals, managers are associated with 2.26% less likely to be severely poor, and 2.29% less likely to be moderate poor with 4.56% more likely to be non-poor.

The same to someone working in Services and sales workers is 1.177% less likely to be severely poor, 1.76% less likely to be moderate poor and 3.5% more likely to be non-poor.

Those working in Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers have 7% more likely to be severely poor and 6% more likely to be moderate poor and also 17% less likely to be non-poor. And about sector of work we analyze this sector of work : **NGO local, international organization and other specify** private non-farm, private farm, public therefore by one unit change these work. In Private non-farm they have chance 5.3% less likely to be severely poor, and 5.2% less likely to be moderate poor ,10% more likely to be non-poor ,Similarly, someone working in private farm there 2.6% less likely to be severely poor ,2.8% less likely to be moderate poor and 5.4% more likely to be non-poor .and for those working in public sector 3.9% more likely to be severely poor ,4% more likely to be moderate poor and 7% less likely to be non-poor.

The variables in occupation status there are not significant to the 5% this implies that the variables in occupation status do not explain the reduction of poverty, it can be caused by the complexity in defining a variable of occupation status.

4.6. Household characteristics

Education plays a critical role in categorizing individuals along with the poverty status. The education variables include: households not educated, having primary education, secondary and more level of education. this is critical because employment is based on the educational qualifications of individuals. We see that all level of education reduces the chance of the households being poor. the result shows that an increase 1 units of odds that someone having primary education is associated with 3.8% less likely to be severely poor,3.5% less likely to be moderate poor and 7.44% more likely to be non-poor. Similarly, to those who have secondary education and more 3.74% are less likely to be severely poor,3.4% less likely to be moderate poor and 7.2% more likely to be non-poor, The study also shows that the gender of households to poverty status which indicates that the gender of households was not significant in predicting the poverty reduction to households.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Summary

This chapter presents the summary of the research on the impact of employment on poverty reduction in Rwanda. The poverty status involves many areas of the study which affects many predictive variables and therefore the research used ordered logit model to find out the relationships between different associated variables. It has been observed other things equal, that the labor force participation of the household heads in private non-farm activities is strongly negatively related to poverty because earning in labor markets are the main source of income for poor. However, a participant in the labor force is not guaranteed for not being poor when working in low productivity occupation. What needs here is more quality of the labor force. This will result in health labor supply, which is one of the most important factors of economic productivity that increase the real wages and turns to reduce poverty.

According to survey of (NISR, EICV Survey, 2015) which was focused on poverty as measured in Rwanda, this study also line up the relationship between different explanatory variables like education level of respondent, gender, occupation and their respective sector of work. The study mention that individuals who have primary education or secondary and more are more likely to be non-poor. Additionally, there is no significant probability of gender to poverty status in this case. The odds ratio of someone working in private farm are negatively correlated to severely poor which means that the household head working as the private farm is more likely to reduce his or her chance off falling under severely poor.

5.2. Conclusion

5.2.1 Characteristics of employment's variables to poverty reduction

most of the private farm is in the informal sector followed by private non-farm employees work in the formal sector. The vast majority of these working in the informal sector includes those working in small family farms. According to integrated household living condition (EICV5), the net job between 2017/2018 THE 19% is farm-based job while 81% are non-farm-based job.

the education outcome is also improving according to (NISR, Thematic report, 2018) with net attendance in primary education of 87.6% and for secondary education of 23.2% almost his

improving the level of tertiary education where the education attainment has a negative correlation with severely and moderately poor. This is because most of the service and sales employees are educated persons, even for those who are in the private sector they create jobs based on the previous knowledge acquired in their study, therefore education background touches those explanatory variables which decrease poverty status as we have presented that level of education is statistically significant to poverty reduction. The study suggests that individuals with education backgrounds are more likely to be non-poor because of the lower ability to be overworked on resources and technology which comes along with higher education, the lower the chance of having limited resources. Education is vital for boosting the productivity of human factors and making people more aware of productivities for earning a living or income generation from non-farm sources based. For this reason, it is noted that labor is by far the most important asset of the poor and increasing their education will, in turn, increase labor productivity and wages which ultimately will reduce their poverty status. Further evidence was given by (Grootart, 1997), to confirm that there is a link between education attainment, the income-earning potential of the household and poverty. He states that there is a minimum level of education necessary to enhance appreciation and adaptation of new technology that can be an instrument in increasing household productivity and thereby earn more income. The increased income will enable households to move out of poverty.

5.2.2. Occupation status with poverty status

Main occupation status is very important in poverty reduction. The study demonstrates that there is a high chance for someone employed in Technical and associate professionals, managers, Services, and sales workers to be non-poor. This mentions that main occupation helps individuals to earn a living and free themselves out of poverty. Where these employments require some skills to perform well this also shows growth in job innovation and creation in Rwanda. Thus, there is no doubt that most of this increase has been the solution to unemployment.

5.2.3. Job sector with poverty status

The study has shown that a unit increase in any of job sectors is associated to less likely categorized as severely poor and less likely categorized as moderately poor and more likely categorized as non-poor. This sector involves both private non-wages and private wages and public. However, private non-wage farms are categorized with informal and formal employment.

However informal employment represents the large share of the population in Rwanda, therefore, those with informal are at risk of no paid., understanding the link between informal employment, poverty, and human development are critical for formulating policy

5.2.4.level of education with poverty status

the study presents the importance of education to the living standard of Rwandans. This will be shown that someone with an education level will tend to earn more jobs ,it also implies that someone who has secondary education and more can work in private non-farm and liberate him/her self from poverty .in other words someone who has attained secondary level or more must undergo at least basic education and have acquired enough skills which enable her to identify opportunities and develop strategies to tap into different ventures.

The study show how a unit change in secondary and more is able to reduce poverty this means that higher education and vocational training play a vital role in poverty reduction because many people free out poverty through employment than by getting more skills to enable them to become competitive on labor market as well as empowering them to become self-employed.it can be also easy to them to create jobs and therefore increasing employment rate for poor households in Rwanda

5.3.Conclusion

According to (Krugman, 1994) as well as wage, labor productivity is an important factor for investment, a key resource for growth and competition. labor productivity has a significant role in poverty reduction for two reasons:

First productivity increase profits to the poor directly by increasing agriculture yields from the family business and raises the earnings of workers (Ravallion, 1998) , secondly, it can reduce the prices of goods, which benefit to both rural and urban poor, thus Rwanda needs enough employment paying wages to change people life condition

From the research, it was observed that the majority of people engage in private wages and non-wage sector. The statistics in the model have presented that there is a negative relationship between private farm and private non-farm to poverty status this means that it reduces poverty at a good level for better living condition of Rwandans this can predict two aspects one people in private farm practice the farming modern methods and two people in private non-farm have great capacity to perform their work ss both it reduces the probability of being poor, education level also decreases the probability of being poor

The gender of household's head has no influence on poverty reduction similarly to main job status which is not statistically significant to explain poverty reduction

the hypothesis that household characteristics and employment variables have a significant role in explaining poverty status of the household.

The analysis present above enables policymakers to clearly see the impact of the household's characteristics and employment variables on poverty status in Rwanda

5.6.Recommendation

This study examined the impact of employment for poverty reduction in Rwanda .by analyzing the household characteristics and employment variables, the analysis show the set of variables that have positive correlation with the probability of being severely poor or moderate poor .this includes: Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers and public sectors from the above findings we can formulate the recommendation's:

First of all, in as much as the government would like to support the agriculture sector and come up with programs to sensitize agriculture sectors through prosper farming methods in order to avoid traditional subsistence farming methods

For those who engaged in the private farm, vocational schools need to be equipped with proper resources to allow the learners to captures the modern innovation comes up with technological changes in the global world. More funds need to be allocated for such technical schools in order to allow efficient transfer of knowledge and skills to learns. There are needs of more efforts to group people in cooperatives working informal sectors .therefore there is a need for government to put effort in investing in human capital in every area of country, educate and create awareness on the benefits of embracing more skilled people and training.in increase government has to help the poor to gain access to finance.

In conclusion, the government of Rwanda must put in place the effort to make people in cooperatively with many parterns and to make the achievement of results.we also individuals living in poverty must working collaboratively with governments at all stages in developing and implementating actions that will reduce or alleviate poverty and in long term to prevent poverty for the next generation,therefore it is very necessary to to ensure that all public policies and the programs ,services working to alleviate and prevent poverty in our country of Rwanda.

References

Bibliography

- Chambers. (1983). RURAL development .
- Churchuchill. (1991). principal methods. *appraisal and utilization*.
- Development, W. (2003). Assessing the Extent and Nature of Chronic Poverty in Low Income Countries. *Issues and Evidence*.
- Gaag, G. (1990). Identifying the poor in developing countries. *WORLD DEVELOPMENT*.
- Grootart, c. (1997). The determinants of poverty in cote d'Ivoire. *Africa Economies*.
- Groov, B. (2001). quantitative analysis.
- Haroon, B. (2016). Growth trap and opportunities for six african economies. *Africans Lions*.
- Islam, R. (2004). The Nexus of Economic Growth, Employment and Poverty Reduction: .
- Jalan. (2005). Poverty Lines . *Poverty Manual*.
- Jalan, R. (n.d.). *income Gains to the Poor from Workfare*. WORLD BANK.
- Kanbur. (1990). Rural poverty in developing countries,. *issues and policies* .
- Khandker, H. J. (2009). “Poverty and Inequality:” hand Book on poverty and Inequality. *The world Bank D.C* .
- Krugman. (1994). past and prospective cause of higher unemployment. *economic policy*.
- Lewis, A. (2006). *WORLD WEB DICTIONALY* . NEWYORK: UNIVERSITY OF PRINCETON.
- Mansfield, E. (1986). Pantents and innovation.
- Marija. (2001). multivariate analysis.
- MFPED. (1999). Knowing poverty.
- Micheal, M. (2010). Job insecurity and health. *A study of 16 European countries*.
- NISR. (2015). EICV Survey .
- NISR. (2018). *Thermatic report*.

- OECD. (2009). Promoting pro-poor Growth Employment.
- Olu, A. (2009). Understanding the relationship between growth and employment in Nigeria .
WIDER Working .
- Paul, D. (2013). PROPRIETY IN INDIVIDUAL CHOICE, MORAL JUDGMENT, AND POLITICS.
- Pedro, M. (2013). Growth,employment and poverty in Africa. *Tales of Lions and Cheetahs*.
- Ravallion. (1998). Growth and redistribution change in poverty measure . *development economy*.
- Rizwanul, I. (2004). The Nexus of Economic Growth, Employment and Poverty Reduction. *Issues in Employment and Poverty* .
- Schultz. (1991). introduction to human capital.
- Sen. (1983). capability approach. *grobal povert research* .
- shaffer. (2001). he Tug of Work and Family. *Direct and Indirect Domain-Specific Determinants of Work-Family Conflict*.
- Townsend. (2003). The meaning of poverty' and contemporary quantitative poverty .
- UNDP. (2007). Poverty,social exclusion and health system in thE european region .
- Wachter. (1974). secondary labor market.
- WORDLD, B. (1999). *Assessment report*.
- WORLD, B. (2010). Annual report.
- WORLD, B. (2018). *changing nature of work*.